

Extraction of Cadmium(II)-Phenanthroline Complex on Polyurethane Foam using Dithizone as Counter-ion for its Spectrophotometric Determination in Commercial Zinc Oxides

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A spectrophotometric method for the determination of Cd^{II} in low concentration upto $0.05 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ after selective extraction of Cd^{II} -phenanthroline complex on polyurethane foam sorbents using dithizone as counter-ion has been developed. Interferences of metal ions such as Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Fe^{II} upto $100 \mu\text{g}$, Zn^{II} upto $8000 \mu\text{g}$ and Pb^{II} upto $1000 \mu\text{g}$ have automatically been eliminated in the presence of 1,10-phenanthroline. Cu^{II} ($50 \mu\text{g}$) interferes in the determination of Cd ($20 \mu\text{g}$) which has been eliminated by masking with EDTA. F^- ion does not interfere in the method. The method has been applied to various Zn-bearing materials.

Determination of Cd in trace quantities creates problem in presence of Zn due to their identical chemical behaviour¹. Extraction of cationic Cd-phen complex with perchlorate ion in presence of Zn with nitrobenzene from weakly acidic solution has been reported^{3,4}. Akaiwa *et al.*⁵ extracted Cd^{II} -phen complex into CHCl_3 at pH ~3 with Cl^- as counter-ion and determined Cd spectrophotometrically by converting $\text{Cd}(\text{phen})_3\text{Cl}_2$ to $\text{Cd}(\text{HDz})_2(\text{phen})$. With the introduction of polyurethane foam (PUF) as a 'solid solvent' in analytical chemistry, considerable interest aroused for its wide application in separation, pre-concentration and determination of desired elements⁶. Several extraction procedures have been reported by earlier workers for Cd from water using polyurethane foam loaded with benzoylacetone⁷, pyridylazonaphthol (PAN)⁸ and methyltricaprylammonium chloride (Aliquat 336)⁹. But no study has yet been reported on the selective sorption as well as quantitative determination of Cd^{II} -phen complex with dithizone as counter-ion in presence of Zn on unloaded PUF.

The present communication establishes the different parameters for selective and quantitative sorption of Cd^{II} -phen-dithizone complex on unloaded polyurethane foam, in order to develop a spectrophotometric method for determination of small amounts of Cd in Zn-bearing materials.

Results and Discussion

It has been observed that Cd^{II} forms a cationic phenanthroline complex at pH 2-3 which is sorbed on PUF using dithizone as counter-ion and appears green. Dithizone itself sorbed on PUF at this pH also imparts an anionic green colour. However, there is a sharp difference in the absorbance characteristics of the blank and Cd solution when measured with a spectrophotometer. In case of Cd^{II} complex maximum absorbance is obtained at 608 nm without a peak in the lower region, whereas in case of dithizone

alone two distinct peaks are observed ($610, 450 \text{ nm}$)². This observation confirms the formation and sorption of Cd-phen-dithizone complex on PUF through ion-association. The sorbed phase eluted in acetone gives reddish pink solution after making alkaline with 0.2 ml of 2.5 M NH_3 solution. This reddish pink solution gives a distinct peak at 510 nm which is a characteristic peak² of $\text{Cd}(\text{HDz})_2$, confirming that the complex $\text{Cd}(\text{phen})_n(\text{HDz})_2$ initially sorbed on PUF as an ion-association complex is ultimately converted to reddish pink $\text{Cd}(\text{HDz})_2(\text{phen})$ where phenanthroline acts as an adduct. This was further corroborated by comparing the absorbance curve of $\text{Cd}(\text{HDz})_2(\text{phen})$ with that of $\text{Cd}(\text{HDz})_2$ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (A) $\text{Cd}(\text{HDz})_2$ and (B) $\text{Cd}(\text{HDz})_2(\text{phen})$ in ammoniacal acetone medium

Therefore, all subsequent studies on the extraction of Cd^{II} have been carried out by extracting Cd(phen)(HDz)₂ on PUF from the solution at pH 2.0, eluting and converting this complex with ammoniacal acetone to Cd(HDz)(phen) followed by measuring the absorbance of the solution at 510 nm.

However, in order to produce a quantitative yield of the phase Cd(HDz)₂(phen), the following parameters have been optimised : (i) concentration of phenanthroline, (ii) concentration of dithizone and (iii) equilibration time.

Concentration of phenanthroline : Concentration of 1,10-phenanthroline was varied from 0 (blank) to $7.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ keeping all other factors, such as metal ion, dithizone concentrations constant. Following the experimental procedure, the results indicate that maximum absorption is attained at $3 \times 10^{-2} M$ phenanthroline concentration.

Concentration of dithizone : The effect of dithizone was also studied as above by varying dithizone concentration from 1.95×10^{-5} to $7.80 \times 10^{-5} M$, and maximum extraction of Cd-phen-dithizonate has been obtained at $5.85 \times 10^{-5} M$.

Equilibration time : Equilibration time to achieve maximum extraction with PUF was studied by adding a series of Cd solution ($10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) to solutions having the same concentrations of $3 \times 10^{-2} M$ phenanthroline and $5.85 \times 10^{-5} M$ dithizone in a total volume of 20 ml at pH 2.0 following the experimental procedure. It requires 45 min for quantitative extraction of Cd. Temperature of extraction was also optimised by performing experiments as above by varying the temperature between 20 and 45° and keeping the equilibration time fixed (45 min). Optimum temperature as observed is $30 \pm 5^\circ$, above which the complex gradually dissociates.

Apart from Zn, the interfering effect of Pb is also serious. However, their effect can be eliminated by adding an excess of 1,10-phenanthroline during extraction. A 10-fold excess of Mn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} do not interfere for determination of $10 \mu\text{g}$ of Cd. Cu interferes seriously and its effect can be overcome by masking with EDTA. The presence of F causes no harm.

Based on the above observations, a method has been developed and standardised with simulated solutions of Cd and the results compared with those obtained by AAS. The method was also applied to determine Cd in different commercial samples of Zn oxide, Zn-bearing materials and ceramic articles where the presence of Cd in the composition is limited by toxicity and the results are in good agreement with the values obtained by AAS for Cd. Standard deviation of the results was found to be ± 0.024 .

The method is more sensitive having a lower detection limit than other solvent extraction techniques, as the PUF has 10 to 100-folds more extraction capacity than any other

liquid solvent⁶. The regression analysis shows the co-relation coefficient of the linear curve to be 0.9998.

Experimental

A Spectromom 361 spectrophotometer was used.

All reagents were of A.R. or G.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. An aqueous 1,10-phenanthroline solution (0.2 M; pH 2) and a 0.03% methanolic dithizone solution were used. Treated PUF¹⁰ was used.

Ammonia solution (50 ml) was treated by dipping in it polyurethane foam chips (2.5 cm l, 0.5 cm dia; 10–12 pieces) loaded with 0.01% dithizone in acetylacetone and equilibrated for 30 min with squeezing the chips at an interval of 5 min by a polythene plunger. The foam pieces were then discarded and the purified ammonia solution (2.5 M) was used throughout the study.

A $1000 \mu\text{g Cd/ml}$ solution was prepared by dissolving CdCl₂.2H₂O in double-distilled water and then diluted to 1 dm^3 and standardised¹¹ against EDTA at pH 5.0. Then 5.0 and 0.5 $\mu\text{g Cd/ml}$ solutions were prepared by proper dilution.

Procedure : Cd solution (1–10 ml) containing 0.5–20 $\mu\text{g Cd}$ was diluted with water (15 ml) and pH was adjusted to 2. Then solutions of 0.2 M 1,10-phenanthroline (3 ml) and 0.03% dithizone (1 ml) were added to it and the volume was made upto 20 ml. The chips (8 pieces) were put into the solution and squeezed at 15 min interval for a period of at least 50 min at room temperature. Then the foam chips were transferred to a syringe (5 ml) and washed thoroughly with water (4 times), ammonia (2.5 M) and finally with water. The complex was then eluted with acetone (2 ml each time), the eluted solution made alkaline with 2.5 M ammonia solution (2.0 ml) and the volume made upto 10 ml with acetone. Absorbance of the eluted solution was measured at 510 nm against a reagent blank.

Determination of Cd in Zn materials : The sample (0.2 g dried at 110°) was dissolved in 6 M HCl (5 ml) by heating on a sand-bath. In case of ceramics, the sample (0.2 g) was decomposed with a mixture of HF (10 ml) and 18 N H₂SO₄ (10 ml) on a sand-bath until the fuming of SO₂. The volume of the clear solution was then made up to 100 ml with water. An aliquot (5 ml) of this solution was evaporated to near dryness on a water-bath, the residue dissolved in 1 M HCl (2 ml) by heating. The solution was diluted with water (4 ml), its pH adjusted to 2 by adding 1.5 M ammonia solution. Volume at this stage was kept 9 ml. Then solutions of 0.2 M phenanthroline (10 ml) and 0.03% dithizone (1 ml) were added, final volume was made upto 20 ml and Cd determined by following the above procedure.

By following the above procedure, calibration curves of standard working solutions containing 0–0.5 and 0.5–2.0

$\mu\text{g Cd/ml}$ were drawn. For both the cases the curves obeyed Beer's law.

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